

BIOcean5D

Policy brief detailing recommendations for ocean governance process:

Ratifying and Implementing the High Seas (BBNJ) Treaty

This Policy document will foster the objectives and strategies for the BBNJ implementation and for the links with the UN Ocean Conference, which will be held in June 2025 in Nice, France (UNOC25).

Co-funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement number	101059915
Call	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-0
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-03
Type of Action	HORIZON-RIA
Project title	MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL AND HUMAN SCALES
Project acronym	BIOcean5D
Deliverable title	Policy briefs detailing recommendations for ocean governance process
Deliverable number	D7.2
Version	vn-1.04
Document status	Draft
Type	DEC - Websites, patent filing, videos etc.
Diffusion	PU - Public
Related Work Package	WP7 Outreach, engagement and use of results
Task	T7.2
Full lead beneficiary	FTO - Fondation Tara Ocean
Author(s) and Affiliations	Andre Abreu (FTO), Eva Matescot (FTO)
Project Officer	Victoria Beaz Hidalgo
Due date	M18 31.05.2024
Submission date	31.05.2024
Total number of pages	17
Keywords	Ocean Policy; Monitoring tools; Ocean Governance;

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
Version history	4
List of Acronyms	5
Executive Summary	6
1. Background Information	6
1.1. Workshop	6
1.2. Joint Session	7
1.3. Hands-on Scientific Activities and Dialogue between Policymakers and Scientists on ocean observation, scientific cooperation, and capacity-building/transfer of marine technology	7
2. Key Points	7
2.1. Key points from the workshop.	7
2.1.1. Role of the scientific community	7
2.1.2. BBNJ Batch Identifier (BBNJ Identifier)	7
2.1.3. Emerging technologies (e.g., eDNA, autonomous vehicles, citizen science, etc.) in the context of the BBNJ Treaty's benefit sharing associated with MGRs/DSI (Part II)	8
2.1.4. Existing and emerging IT technologies that may best handle information generated as part of the MGR requirements.	8
2.1.5. Applied research activities that use DSI and how the BBNJ Treaty can support robust research activities.	9
2.1.6. International cooperation, research funding and capacity-building/transfer of marine technology.	9
2.1.7. Coordination between the BBNJ Treaty's Scientific and Technical Body (STB) and subsidiary bodies.	10
2.1.8. Capacity-building and funding on ratification and implementation.	11
2.2. Key points from the Joint Session	12
2.2.1. Ratification and implementation: challenges and opportunities	12
2.2.2. The 2025 UN Ocean Conference (UNOC) and next steps	12
3. Key Questions for the Next steps of the implementation dialogue	12

Version history

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	Hiroko Muraki Gottlieb / André Abreu (FTO)	Initial draft	28.04.2024
0.2	Andre Abreu (FTO)	Revised draft	15.05..2024
0.3	André Abreu / Eva Matescot (FTO)	Preliminary version	26.05.2024
0.4	André Abreu/Eva Matescot / Hiroko Muraki Gottlieb	Final version	25.06.2024

List of Acronyms

ABMT	Area-Based Management Tool
AFD	Agence Française de Développement
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BBNJ	Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
COP	Conference of the Parties
DOALOS	The Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea
DSI	Digital Sequence Information
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
GEF	Global Environment Facility
IBM	International Business Machines
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISA	International Seabed Authority
IT	Information Technology
LTC	Legal and Technical Commissions
MGR	Marine Genetic Resources
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
STB	Scientific and Technical Body
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNOC	United Nations Ocean Conference
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organisation

Executive Summary

This document provides a summary and recommendations stemming from the workshop held in Nice, France, from 10-12 April 2024. The Tara Ocean Foundation and the Girguis Lab at Harvard University co-hosted the high-level dialogue and capacity-building to contribute to an early entry into force of the BBNJ Treaty. The topics covered and the capacity-building activities in the workshop will foster the objectives and strategies for the UN Ocean Conference, which will be held in June 2025 in Nice, France (UNOC25). This document compiles the questions for future work, as well as the next steps.

1. Background Information

The workshop had three distinct but related parts. The first part, the workshop, covered technical discussions about the topics listed below. The second part, the joint session, focused on strengthening the political will to accelerate the ratification process for the signatories, globally. The final part, the scientific activities and dialogue between policymakers and scientists, involved hands-on experience in *in-situ* collection, storage, and post-collection lab processing. The meetings were held under the Chatham House Rule and all participants engaged in their personal capacity.

1.1. Workshop

The workshop covered the following topics:

1. The role of scientists to effectively implement the Marine Genetic Resources (MGR) requirements—challenges and opportunities.
2. Dialogue between scientists and policymakers on the BBNJ Batch Identifier.
3. Dialogue between scientists and policymakers on the emerging technologies (e.g., eDNA, autonomous vehicles, etc.) that need to be considered for the MGR requirements.
4. Dialogue among an IT expert, scientists, and policymakers on the existing and emerging IT technologies that may best handle information generated as part of the MGR requirements.
5. Dialogue between scientists and policymakers on applied research activities that use digital sequence information and how the BBNJ Treaty can support robust research activities.
6. International cooperation, research funding and capacity-building/transfer of marine technology.
7. Coordination between the BBNJ Treaty's Scientific and Technical Body and subsidiary bodies.
8. Capacity-building and funding on ratification and implementation.

1.2. Joint Session

The joint session covered the following topics:

1. Ratification and implementation: challenges and opportunities.
2. The UN Ocean Conference and next steps.

1.3. Hands-on Scientific Activities and Dialogue between Policymakers and Scientists on ocean observation, scientific cooperation, and capacity-building/transfer of marine technology

Tara schooner (*Tara*) is a scientific boat that has been conducting open and inclusive scientific expeditions for more than 20 years. *Tara's* community of partners is prioritising the exploration of the Ocean microbiome, working with Digital Sequence Information (DSI) (genetics, genomics) on issues directly linked to the BBNJ Treaty. In Nice, the participants experienced an hour-and-a half cruise on *Tara* with scientists who explained how the *in-situ* samples are collected and how they build the pipeline of data from the vessel to the scientific collections and digital databases. Further, policymakers toured a historic marine laboratory in Villefranche (LOV) and learned from scientists how research is conducted on organisms collected from the ocean. Finally, scientists and policymakers engaged in a lively discussion about the BBNJ Treaty and opportunities for fostering capacity-building and for the transfer of marine technology.

2. Key Points

2.1. Key points from the workshop.

2.1.1. Role of the scientific community

- Science has always been integral to Ocean governance and the BBNJ Treaty is no exception.
- Input from the stakeholders involved at the national level is critical, for both developed and developing countries/regions.

2.1.2. BBNJ Batch Identifier (BBNJ Identifier)

- The BBNJ Treaty has already positively impacted International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC). The ability to label sampling records could additionally impact the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Pandemic Treaty discussions. INSDC's new process could be an example of how data can be labelled to increase scientific value. The BBNJ Identifier will be discussed at the INSDC meeting in June 2024.
- As for the BBNJ Identifier, the Clearing House Mechanism (CHM) will need to be designed and operational to effectively communicate with INSDC. The BBNJ Identifier could contribute to global standardisation, but limitations will always exist. For example,

INSDC cannot say whether anyone used it. Also, capacity-building and the value of labelling need to be communicated to the scientific community (institutions).

- The Scientific and Technical Body's role (STB) in the benefit sharing associated with MGRs needs to be clarified.
- For the samples that were collected prior to entry into force, we could look at how World Intellectual Property Organisation's Standard 26 uses automatic submission of patents when entering data into the INSDC database, which gives a tag "/PAT." COP and the subsidiary bodies may consider if a similar tag for the retroactive DSI and samples that's standardised across BBNJ may work with the CIHM and the MGR/DSI benefit sharing (Part II) obligations.
- The costs of updating INSDC can only be estimated once more information about the CIHM functions and other BBNJ Identifier-related obligations are clarified. There is a question about who should finance and what "reasonable costs" entail. Costs to maintain databases could be high, thus the need to merge discussions on the allocation of work necessary between CIHM and the existing databases.

2.1.3. Emerging technologies (e.g., eDNA, autonomous vehicles, citizen science, etc.) in the context of the BBNJ Treaty's benefit sharing associated with MGRs/DSI (Part II)

- The current use of eDNA is more about understanding biodiversity than applied research, such as drug discovery. The BBNJ Treaty does not cover marine living resources broadly, but rather marine genetic resources. How can we ensure that we are not inadvertently capturing a broader scope of collection than was intended by the negotiators? eDNA could be helpful for Area-based Management Tools (ABMTs), including Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs).
- The BBNJ Treaty establishes a framework, and the Conference of the Parties (COP) with the support of its subsidiary bodies will need to fill in the framework's gaps. Many questions remain regarding emerging technologies, in particular, related to eDNA, citizen science, autonomous instruments, non-invasive gene sequencing without taking a biological sample. Items to keep in mind include an implementable system, the original purpose of the BBNJ Treaty, the purpose of Part II, the scope of *in situ* collection of MGR, how to facilitate science, how the benefits are being generated. There should be a flexible, systemic approach to handling emerging technologies and advancement in science. Compliance with the Part II requirements needs to be easy, especially for the scientists from developing country and citizen scientists.

2.1.4. Existing and emerging IT technologies that may best handle information generated as part of the MGR requirements.

- In terms of IT architecture, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has evolved from expert systems, machine learning, and deep learning to Foundation Models. There has been a

fundamental shift in AI Algorithms, techniques, and tools. Foundation Models can self-supervise at scale, deal with massive data, and compute. Foundation Models are being applied to climate and sustainability in the private sector and at institutions (e.g., IBM and NASA partnership for weather and climate).

- More needs to be understood as to the existing and emerging IT architecture to best support the design, implementation, and management of the Clearing-House Mechanism.

2.1.5. Applied research activities that use DSI and how the BBNJ Treaty can support robust research activities.

- Engagement by all stakeholders for technical information sharing is important, not only at the BBNJ Preparatory Commission level, but also domestically.
- There may be an opportunity to consider a single infrastructure for DSI and to facilitate harmonisation. We need this same type of discussion in other international agreement fora, including the CBD processes.
- The domestic Nagoya Protocol legislation of Brazil supports those who comply to use it for publicity, however, there is currently no “certification.”
- The Part II provisions need to be fully operationalised to provide robust support of research activities. To that end, COP needs to balance capturing monetary benefits vs. conserving biodiversity.
- The COP must ensure the STB includes scientists from developing countries so they are not left behind.
- A strong recognition to build on existing scientific processes and infrastructure. There may be an opportunity to consider a single infrastructure for DSI.

2.1.6. International cooperation, research funding and capacity-building/transfer of marine technology.

- The COP, with the support of its subsidiary body, needs to keep in mind how to capture genuine connections, not just having *ad-hoc* participation of insufficiently informed members. This type of mismatch examples are numerous and frequent globally. Coordination of agencies at the domestic level is paramount.
- There needs to be capacity-building to support scientists from developing country in obtaining funding. Currently, funding is given to scientists from developed countries because they have the know-how on funding.
- There are other challenges associated with research funding. For example, in the US, the funding tends to be reserved for citizens and is short-term project-based. The funding rules also seem to differ from agency to agency. Currently, National Sciences Foundation and National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration fundings do not allow funding scientists from other countries, except for providing some participant costs. However, the US Navy can fund scientists from other countries. On the other hand, some funding in France requires the inclusion of scientists from developing countries.

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) specifically states that there is no obligation to pay for the scientists' salary, which could contribute to the funding problem.

- The Swedish International Development Agency funding model may be the best, which is long-term and needs-based. The International Foundation of Science also funds research along with mentorship.
- The research/academic culture needs to change so that there is full recognition in fostering international cooperation and capacity-building/transfer of marine technology, especially in association with the developing countries. The recognition of this effort could lead to tenure, promotion, salary increase, awards, etc.
- The Clearing-House Mechanism could be useful for the transfer of marine technology, but there are logistical challenges, for example, customs related to the marine scientific research consent regime. As an incentive, some benefits could be given if the transfer of marine technology is BBNJ related (e.g., customs discounts, a fast-track process for marine scientific research, etc.).
- The Clearing-House Mechanism could be a useful tool. However, it may be helpful to engage with UNESCO-Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission to find out lessons learned on its match-making system and on responding to needs assessment with relevant resources.

2.1.7. Coordination between the BBNJ Treaty's Scientific and Technical Body (STB) and subsidiary bodies.

- Coordination/cooperation across all the subsidiary bodies must be set up and maintained. The terms of reference of the STB are still to be approved. This is the opportunity to think thoroughly how to promote integration, reduce overlapping, and avoid in-fighting. It will be important to determine all subsidiary bodies' terms of reference at the first COP.
- There are many aspects to consider, in terms of the composition of the STB membership: 1. Qualifications, 2. Scientists who are actively conducting research, 3. Field of expertise (e.g., data science, modelling, traditional knowledge, etc.), 4. Geographical representation, etc. The criteria themselves and the decision-making process will be critical.
- Would the STB have the power to set up expert groups or consult with external stakeholders? For example, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) allows scientists who are not members to still provide input.
- The Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) committee will rely on advice of the STB, and the terms of reference and modalities will be crucial to get the interplay right to allow for efficient decision-making by the COP.
- We may look to the International Seabed Authority's (ISA) Legal and Technical Commission (LTC) for lessons learned. More than 40% of the members are somehow related to mining activities and not to environmental aspects. Also, there is a significant

lack of transparency within ISA's LTC. The BBNJ Treaty's STB and other subsidiary bodies need to avoid such practices.

- The STB could have a very important role in advising the COP. We may look at the IPCC model, where it is rare for the COP to change the recommendation of its subsidiary body.

2.1.8. Capacity-building and funding on ratification and implementation.

- The Global Environment Facility (GEF) issued the initial guidelines on applying for funds in February 2024 (GEF/C.66/07). The guideline provides detailed information about the GEF's funding scheme for the work related to the BBNJ Treaty. There are two tracks for obtaining funds: a. \$29 million total for individual GEF eligible countries to apply to get \$175K each; b. 5 million regional - this goes through one of the GEF agencies (e.g., UNDP, FAO, UNEP).
- The Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea (DOALOS), as the interim secretariat for the BBNJ Treaty, will conduct various capacity-building activities to promote a better understanding of the Treaty and prepare for entry into force. DOALOS will also facilitate inter-agency coordination and cooperation of the UN system in supporting the entry into force and implementation of the Treaty.
- DOALOS and GEF conducted a capacity-building and technical assistance needs survey. The key takeaways are: a. improve understanding of the BBNJ Treaty among government officials, b. technical assistance with national law/regulation/policy, c. preparation of government agencies for entry into force, d. interest in activities relating to key issues under the Treaty, as well as financial resources and mechanisms, e. streamlined and building on previous activities as soon as possible, f., activities at national and regional levels, along with substantive financial support.
- DOALOS conducts the following capacity-building work: a. capacity needs and priority assessments (including a toolkit), b. regional workshops, c. national technical assistance, d. briefings, e. side events, f. outreach materials, g. interim open access website for the Treaty. This project is funded by the European Union (1.4M€).
- It would be important to keep the old BBNJ Treaty open access website (or the content thereof) because of the rich resources it entails.
- The European Union's commitment to provide 40M€ is subject to approval, and the final decision will be made after this summer. The funds will likely support a wide range of projects and could support new or existing initiatives.
- L'Agence Française de Développement (AFD) is providing funding to support the 2025 UN Ocean Conference. The AFD has not funded BBNJ Treaty-related projects, but there may be some scope for funding. There is complementarity with the French Facility for Global Environment.

2.2. Key points from the Joint Session

2.2.1. Ratification and implementation: challenges and opportunities

- One factor that supported early ratification for Chile and Seychelles was a strong support by the Head of State and the high-level officials:
 - Chile: accelerated process supported by the President and unanimous approval by the Senate.
 - Seychelles: acceptance by the parliament, judiciary, and ministers was relatively smooth because of the importance of the blue economy for the country.
- There are initiatives in various regions and countries on capacity building within the region and ongoing work towards ratification. Each region and country have their unique challenges, but there is momentum for reaching 60 Parties as soon as possible.
- Sharing the lessons learned from countries that have ratified the BBNJ Treaty would be invaluable for those going through the ratification process. The benefits of becoming a Party need to be communicated broadly.

2.2.2. The 2025 UN Ocean Conference (UNOC) and next steps

- Signatories are already using the 2025 UNOC as a milestone for securing 60 Parties.
- UNOC is an incredible opportunity to showcase the opportunities associated with the BBNJ Treaty.
- *Tara* and the Girguis Lab could host a follow-up workshop in November 2024.

3. Key Questions for the Next steps of the implementation dialogue

The following are key questions that could be explored to support the Preparatory Commission's work:

- What are some critical terms of reference to ensure that the Scientific and Technical Body achieve its mandates?
- What could be the work of the Preparatory Scientific and Technical Body?
- Are observational research activities (e.g., eDNA samples, etc.) within the scope of benefit-sharing associated with MGRs? What are the opportunities/challenges?
- What is the science that BBNJ Treaty is trying to foster? Exploration of such questions may begin to answer what marine scientific research the BBNJ Treaty could prioritise.
- What characteristics are important for the design of a Clearing-House Mechanism IT architecture?
- What topics need further thinking/research/dialogue to ensure successful Preparatory Commission meetings?

Corresponding Contact: Andre ABREU
Fondation Tara Ocean
8 Rue de Prague, 75012 Paris
Email: andre@fondationtaraocean.org

Fondation
tara océan
explore and share

Co funded by the European Union (GA# 101059915). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.